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ABSTRACTS

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Comprehensive Machine Learning Framework for Neurological Stress Detection from Physiological Signals

Akshita Singh*¹, Aiswarya S¹, Sneha M L¹, Ashishkrishnan V S¹, Gowtham G. Iyer²,
Manhazy Rashmi¹, Shiva Pratap Gopakumar³, Radhagayathri Udhayakumar²

¹*Amrita School of Engineering, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham, Amritapuri, Kerala, 690525, India*

²*Center for Wireless Networks and Applications, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham, Amritapuri, Kerala-690525, India*

³*The School for Sustainable Development, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham, Amritapuri, Kerala-690525, India*

Abstract: This research paper presents an extension of prior investigations focused on stress detection through non-EEG physiological signals. Leveraging the success of nonlinear feature extraction methods paired with popularly used models in previous studies, our current research explores a more comprehensive extraction of nonlinear features from non-EEG physiological data obtained from 20 subjects experiencing distinct neurological states: relaxation, physical stress, cognitive stress, and emotional stress. In phase 1 of our study the effectiveness of basic linear machine learning models like logistic regression in classifying various neurological states is assessed. Binary and multi-class classification approaches are explored. Under binary classification, we assessed relaxation versus stress. Furthermore, we investigated how these models perform in distinguishing a relaxed state from each specific stress condition, resulting in a four-class classification problem. Building upon this foundation, the next phase of our research expands the binary classification to encompass (a) relaxation versus stress, (b) relaxation versus physical stress, (c) relaxation versus cognitive stress, and (d) relaxation versus emotional stress. We examine the impact of feature reduction techniques including PCA and t-SNE on model performance. Additionally, the study explores the influence of cross-validation methods, such as K-fold and leave-one-out, on refining the model's accuracy and effectiveness in this specific context. The aim of this research is to provide valuable insights into the nuanced interplay of physiological signals and stress states, contributing to the broader understanding of stress detection methodologies.

Keywords: Stress detection, non-EEG physiological signals, nonlinear feature extraction, neurological states, machine learning, dimensionality reduction.

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Rajbaug, Next to Hadapsar, Loni Kalbhor, Pune 412201, India.

+91 744 7444 027 / 28 | +91 914 6051 841 / 42

www.mitbio.edu.in / icrtb@mituniversity.edu.in

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